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TENSIONS ON THE MARITIME BORDER AMONG NORTH AND SOUTH KOREA AND THEIR GEOPOLITICAL IMPACTS ON THE SECURITY OF THE KOREAN PENINSULA

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COUNTRIES & REGIONS: INDO-PACIFIC

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Considering the current geopolitical context, marked by two ongoing wars in the rimland, what is the political risk associated with North Korea's firing on the southern maritime border? On January 6, North Korea fired more than 60 artillery shells near the maritime border with South Korea, raising tensions in the region. The firing carried out by North Korean forces has an impact on the political stability of the Korean peninsula because it was perceived by Seoul as a provocative act, which contributes to the increase in tensions among the two countries. First, let's look at how these events were viewed by the South Korean government.

The artillery fire carried out by Pyongyang's forces was perceived by Seoul as a provocative act. The shooting has happened in the area near of Yeonpyeong Island, which is close to the maritime border with North Korea but belongs to South Korea. According to Yonhap news agency, there were no reports of North Korean artillery shells hitting south of the Northern Limit Line (NLL), a maritime border in the Yellow Sea. Now that we have presented the tension on the maritime border of both countries, let's analyze the severity of its impacts on the Korean peninsula.

The Korean Peninsula is experiencing an increase in geopolitical tensions among the two neighboring countries. South Korea's Defense Ministry has not confirmed whether the decision to evacuate the population of Yeonpyeong Island was prompted by North Korean gunfire or military drills conducted by Seoul's forces in response. Yeonpyeong Island is home to about 2,000 residents and is located approximately 75 miles west of Seoul. After having exposed the recrudescence of inter-Korean relations, we will present another point of view on the tensions on the maritime border among these countries.

Some argue that tension on the maritime border among North and South Korea has been a constant point of friction, as incidents such as exchanges of fire and naval exercises have been recurrent in this region. Although there is this tension on the maritime border, it has reached its neuralgic point due to the suspension of the 2018 Inter-Korean Military Agreement. In fact, the three meetings between North Korean leader Kim Jong Un and South Korean President Moon Jae In, which took place between 2018 and 2019, empirically prove that this agreement acted to mitigate future conflicts on the maritime border, like a "cotton between two crystals".

North Korea's firing on the southern maritime border has had a significant impact on the political stability of the Korean peninsula. Seoul perceived these events as provocative, which resulted in increased tensions in inter-Korean relations. We recommend that stakeholders resume dialogue and choose to invite a third actor to mediate the maritime border conflict, in order to resuming negotiations on the 2018 Inter-Korean Military Settlement. Otherwise, North Korea's nuclear deterrence strategy could increase the political risk of insecurity on the Korean Peninsula, threatening regional peace.

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